

Part I. Guidelines for Inclusive Organisational Structures: Addressing the Institutional Framework of Inclusive Student Mobility

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In this first part of the guidelines for Higher Education Institutions, we offer some recommendations and tools that can assist institutions in the self-assessment and change-management process to establish and improve the mobility management and support structures.

The guidelines are based on the research and data acquisition done during the project and summarise core take-aways for users. The recommendations and templates offered in the Guidelines can help institutions in their own self-assessment process, and can be combined and adapted as deemed useful for the specific institutional context. This process can be initiated on institutional level as well as by individual units, in order to highlight the institutional - and programme-specific context of mobility management, and to apply targeted strategies that match the specific requirements of the institution.

Correlation between Erasmus+ Programme Requirements and Institutional Policies

Based on the analysis of different strategic approaches and designs in HEIs within the project consortium and the associated European University Alliances, we have formulated some general recommendations for the integration of student mobility and the strengthening of inclusive mobility management in the institutional strategy design. The questionnaire used for the Mapping should be applied by institutions to initiate a self-assessment process of the institutional context of student mobility on a strategic and organisational level.

The design and impact of Erasmus+ Mobility Projects rely on the one hand on the external framework set by the Erasmus+ Charter for Higher Education and the relevant regulatory frameworks of the Erasmus+ Programme and the European Educational Area. On the other hand, institutions base their international activities and student exchange management on internal standards defined by institutional strategies on internationalisation, on teaching & learning, as well as on ED&I related thematic fields. Policy statements and strategies of the HE institutions thus have a noticeable impact on

the institutional context of inclusive mobility design as they reflect the university's commitment to overarching priorities and cross-cutting themes, outlining the values, priorities and profile the institution advocates. On a practical level, they serve as a frame of reference for decision-making processes and the distribution of resources.

Recommendations for Institutional Strategy Development

1. **Institutional strategies on internationalisation should explicitly include mobility** – for all members of the institution – as a core element for internationalisation and quality assurance. This can increase visibility and empower staff and participants.
2. **Institutional strategies on internationalisation should explicitly include Equity, Diversity & Inclusion** to strengthen visibility and impact of the discourse for all stakeholders. Even as a cross-cutting topic, explicit positioning of the institution increases commitment and may inform institutional priorities, decisions on change management, resource management etc.

Impact of the ECHE on the institutional Programme design

The Erasmus Charter for Higher Education (ECHE) serves as a value-based regulatory framework which informs programme design and implementation on an institutional level. The HEI commits as a legal entity to the Charter and is accountable for compliance. Therefore, responsibilities for the ECHE criteria are integrated in all levels of the institution. The involvement of all levels and sectors of the institution can strengthen the status and visibility of the programme criteria and associated values. The translation of the regulations and quality criteria into practical processes and actions is then transferred to clearly defined units and individuals, with the central roles of Erasmus+ Institutional Coordinator and proxy explicitly required by the program regulations.

The relevant roles involved in the management and implementation of the Erasmus+ Programme on an organisational level in relation to the ECHE are summarised in the matrix below. Roles involved and responsibilities assigned to the programme on a regulatory level can thereby be transparently defined and communicated for strategic engagement, decision-making processes, and transparent communication.

HEIs should apply this Matrix to review whether all essential roles and responsibilities for Erasmus+ mobility management are clearly assigned within their institution. By checking each role against ECHE compliance, mandatory requirements, and internal

practice, institutions can identify gaps (e.g. missing roles), overlaps, or unclear responsibilities, and use this to strategically improve their organisational structure. In the table, the roles and associated responsibilities involved in the project management of Erasmus+ KA1 Actions are listed and matched to the quality criteria and requirements addressed in the ECHE. This can be differentiated as to a) roles required for the correct implementation of the ECHE, but subject to the institutional organisational specifications; and b) mandatory positions defined by the Erasmus+ Programme as a prerequisite for participation in the Erasmus+ programme.

Table II: Roles & Responsibilities in Erasmus+ Programme Management

Role	Responsibility	Linked to ECHE criteria Y/N	Mandatory Position Y/N	HEI Self-Assessment <i>[comment on internal structure]</i>
Legal Representative	Compliance with ECHE, compliance with other legal frameworks	Y	Y	
HEI leadership (Rector, Vice Rector etc)	Strategy, institutional profile, partnerships; compliance with ECHE	N	N	
Erasmus+ Institutional Coordinator	Overall management of the Erasmus+ Programme; compliance with the principles of the ECHE; international strategy, partnerships	Y	Y	
Erasmus+ Institutional Coordinator Proxy	Formal proxy for above	N	Y	

Erasmus+ Departmental Coordinator	Mobility Management (Outgoing, Incoming) on faculty/department level (advising, selection, quality assurance in learning outcomes, recognition/LA)	Y	N	
Examination Boards	Recognition, compliance with Lisbon convention	Y	N	
Mobility Officer	Compliant Administration of mobilities	Y	N	
Inclusion Officer	Compliance with horizontal pillar inclusion	Y	Y	
Coordinator for Online Language Support	Management of OLS/language support access, compliance with regulations	N	Y	
Administrator for Incoming Services	Integration of students; Visa; accommodation	Y	N	
Financial Department	Financial Management and Monitoring	N	N	
Ombudsperson(s) for participants	Assurance of equal treatment, equal access	Y	N	

<p>Academic Staff</p>	<p>Academic Support for (potential) Outgoing students; Integration of international students in learning environment</p>	<p>N</p>	<p>N</p>	
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Organisational Structures and Programme Design in Student Mobility Management

In the following section, we will describe the tasks and responsibilities in more detail and outline the measures the institution has to implement to fulfil the tasks, and match the tasks with the relevant sections or units of the institution.

To enable institutions to design targeted support and information structures, a clear definition and shared understanding of the priority groups addressed is central. This defines action plans, required knowledge and competences of staff involved, and decides on the assignment of resources, especially budget, in the programme. The identification of specific groups, and the setting of priorities, can be programme-specific, or reflect the overall institutional strategy. Erasmus+ Programme Coordinators should be aware of the overall institutional context to ensure harmonious structures and communication, and to prevent contradictory strategies or conflicting resource planning, to successfully align staff competences with target-group-specific needs, and guide decisions on resources and programme design.

The following table can be used to summarise a structured overview of target groups in student mobility that are addressed in the context of inclusive programme implementation, in order to define and streamline relevant support instruments, plan budget, or assign responsibilities. Support may be based on financial instruments, or on concrete measures for inclusion support per target group.

Table III: Matrix for target-group-oriented support design

Seq. Nr.		Explanation	1	2	[To be cont'd]	
Target group (status group)		[e.g. student, PhD, staff]				
Category Fewer Opportunities* (type of barrier, excluding factor)		[e.g. low income, gender, language]				
Institutional priority group Y/N		[e.g. target groups mentioned in ED&I strategy]				
Target-group-specific support	Financial Support	Eligible for Erasmus+ Social TopUp Y/N				
		Eligible for Erasmus+ inclusion support Y/N				
		Other financial support Y/N	<i>[if Yes, please specify]</i>			
	Other types of support	Support services	<i>[e.g. individual counseling, legal advice, mobility training]</i>			
		Communication	<i>[e.g. translation (incl. sign language/B raille, easy language), online]</i>			

			<i>counseling]</i>			
	Additional information		<i>[e.g. legal/regulatory framework; proof of eligibility]</i>			
Responsible units	Primarily responsible unit/s		<i>[be as specific as possible]</i>			
	Other unit/s to be involved		<i>[be as specific as possible]</i>			

**in reference to the European Pillar of Social Rights (2017), https://employment-social-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies-and-activities/european-pillar-social-rights-building-fairer-and-more-inclusive-european-union_en*

Requirements and Measures for Inclusive Mobility Support

The general requirements deriving from the set-up of international student mobility can be linked to concrete measures. This can be differentiated e.g. for Outgoing and Incoming student mobility, and for inclusivity aspects of mobility design. These can be assigned to specific units or staff, to help create a transparent, well-structured organisational chart, assign tasks, or generate job descriptions in personnel acquisition or management.

The table below presents a practical mapping tool that connects three aspects:

- Requirements that present basic needs that international student mobility generates;
- Measures, or concrete actions or services that can address these programme requirements;
- Responsible Unit or Staff member, or the people and/or offices that should take responsibility for implementing these measures.

HEIs can use this matrix to link core requirements of mobility to concrete measures and assign them to responsible staff or units, creating a transparent organisational chart and clearer job descriptions. To assess your existing programme management structure, or to design an organisational chart for mobility management at your institution, you can

check the list of requirements and associated measures, and assign responsible units or individual staff according to your internal set-up. This table offers an exemplary design and can be extended or adapted according to the institutional needs.

Table IV. Requirements and Measures for Inclusive Mobility Support

Programme Requirement for Student Mobility	Institutional Measure/required tasks	Responsible Unit/ Staff <i>[to be filled in by the HEI]</i>
Programme Information	Accessible information and targeted outreach, using different communication channels	
Accessible Administration	Streamlining administrative processes, reducing administrative barriers	
Organisational Support	Clear guidelines and checklists; clearly defined and accessible contact points for students	
Financial Support	Information on funding opportunities; reliable information on grant rules; information on expected living costs; information about additional financial support	
Accessible Infrastructure & Services	Information on existing infrastructure (eg buildings/classrooms) and support services for targeted support	
Accommodation	Information on local housing market; housing platforms; availability of accessible student accommodation;	

	information on housing costs; contact points	
Academic Information	Course information; structure of course system; examination types, requirements, grading system	
Information on Teaching/Learning Environment	Types of courses, types of collaboration and (co-)learning; transferability of reasonable adjustments	
Language Support	Information in different languages; use of easy language for core information and administrative information; access to language courses & tutoring	
Access to Employment Opportunities	Information on labour market; information on employment laws and work regulations; contact points of career centres	
Social & Cultural Adaptation and Integration	Welcome services; formal and informal networking opportunities, links to peer group; contact points; links to wider community	
Psychological & Medical Support	Information on Services of the HEI; information on health system and insurance; access to/information on medical practices; information on multi-lingual offers; contact points for emergencies	
<i>[Other - please add additional lines according to</i>		

<i>your institution's specific needs]</i>		
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Description of Roles involved in Student Mobility

In the above sections, the analysis focused on the institutional setting and the roles involved in the implementation of inclusive student mobility on a structural level. In the next part, we will focus on a number of core roles involved in student mobility, either on a more strategic or design level, or in the more concrete implementation and administration of the programme.

For the description of relevant roles in the institution in the Guidelines, we have focused on six central categories:

1. Erasmus+ Institutional Coordinator
2. Mobility Officer IRO (Incoming – and Outgoing Mobility)
3. Departmental Coordinator
4. European University Alliance Manager
5. Student Support & Counseling Staff
6. Student Representatives

Other functions in the institution may be involved in inclusive mobility management, and other roles may be defined depending on the institutional setting, but these core roles comprise the central responsibilities and task assignments relevant for our topic.

Descriptions may be transferable to other institutional designs according to the users' requirements.

It is important to clearly define and understand the respective roles, to assess the potential impact on the programme and the target groups. Some roles are essential for the concrete mobility implementation and the support measures, others are at the core of strategy or programme design, change-management, or the assigning of tasks and resources. The specific profiles are relevant to understand the correlations between the various stakeholders involved, and the interdependencies of programme management.

HEIs can use these exemplary role descriptions to assess staff roles in mobility processes within their institution, to assess competence needs, and plan targeted training or support measures to strengthen programme quality. Additionally, the profiles can serve to adapt relevant job descriptions and assess existing roles within the institution. In Part II, these same roles except for Role Nr. 4, European University Alliance Manager, are described in a task-centered design along the phases of the student mobility cycle, adding a step-by-step guideline. The roles included in the two parts differ based on the relevance in the respective analyses, i.e. impact on an institutional and strategic level vs. impact in practical mobility management and -support.

Table V (1-6): Description of Institutional Roles in Mobility Management

1. Erasmus+ Institutional Coordinator	
General description	The Erasmus+ Institutional Coordinator is responsible for programme management, promotion, as well as quality assurance and ECHE compliance. The coordinator is responsible for the projects towards the National Agency and European Commission, and represents the link between institutions and other parties. The coordinator is responsible for dissemination of knowledge and regulations to stakeholders.
Strategic and Policy-Level Involvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Responsible for ECHE compliance, for up-to-date programme and project management ● Link between HEI leadership and institutional stakeholders, National Agency and International Stakeholders (HEI partner institutions, employers etc.) ● Initiates new activity types ● responsible for project acquisition ● Initiates new partnerships/partnership management
Mobility Management & Inclusion Practices	<p>Mobility Management</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Design and implementation of new mobility formats ● Link between needs & expectations from target groups and faculty vs. central strategic decisions, budget considerations and National priorities

	<p>Inclusion Support</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Integration of inclusion categories and measures according to programme requirements and national standards, and translation into institution-specific rules and processes
	<p>Communication & Outreach</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Outreach to faculty/departments ● Information on program regulations, changes/developments in Erasmus+ ● Information on funding schemes, grants and additional support options
<p>Collaboration and Stakeholder Engagement (internal)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Leadership <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ faculty: deans; departmental coordinators; faculty staff; administrative staff in the faculties ● Central administration for different services ● Financial department for budget management & monitoring, grant management ● Legal department for program monitoring, agreement management, financial processing ● HR for staff training opportunities, competence frameworks, certificates

2. Mobility Officer (IRO)	
General description	<p>The Mobility Officers are not involved in the strategic – and policy discourse of the institutions. However, their practical experience and expertise in project administration is a relevant input for the translation and adaptation of Programme regulations and strategic priorities into the mobility process.</p>
Strategic and Policy-Level Involvement	<p><i>[No systematic impact on strategy- or policy level]</i></p>

Mobility Management & Inclusion Practices	<p>Mobility Management</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> administrative mobility processing according to Erasmus+ contractual chain information – and consultation sessions with students and staff to inform on the design of administrative practice grant management
	<p>Inclusion Support</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Information on funding opportunities and D&I related funding rules management of social top-ups reference to internal and external support structures
	<p>Communication & Outreach</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Providing Information on administrative process to students Inform about mobility opportunities (general programme information)
Collaboration and Stakeholder Engagement (internal)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Financial department for grant management IT for management database, student information system, EU online platforms Other administrative units for mobility management process Departmental coordinators Exam boards for LA/ToR process External: partner institutions for mobility management, esp. in pre-arrival/pre-departure phases

3. Departmental Coordinator	
General description	<p>For Outgoing students, the departmental coordinator is often the first point of contact, esp. if their role entails information, selection, and advising on study program, LA and recognition. On the strategic level, departmental</p>

	<p>coordinators are involved on a decentral level, one core topic is the decision on and quality monitoring of Erasmus+ partnerships. This can impact the regional strategies on decentral-, and potentially central level. In quality assurance for partnerships and for mobility tracks, the departmental coordinators play a pivotal role for the management, administration and monitoring of student mobility.</p>
<p>Strategic and Policy-Level Involvement</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Can decide on or co-decide partnership development and strategic priorities in partnerships ● Assess the quality of partnerships and curricula matching ● Identifies viable mobility strands that fit study requirements
<p>Mobility Management & Inclusion Practices</p>	<p>Mobility Management</p> <p>Often responsible for Outgoing- and Incoming students, in different phases of mobility:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Outgoing: Before mobility (advising in application phase, selection, advising in study program abroad/LA), re-entry phase (Recognition of courses) ● Incoming: before/at arrival (preparation of LA, support during arrival phase, Changes to LA, ToR, Departure) <p>Inclusion Support</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Outgoing students: first contact, advising on mobility options and program information ● Incoming students: accessibility of learning environment, integration, individual support <p>Communication & Outreach</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Online promotion, aligned with students' academic calendars ● Information on study-related aspects of mobility (selection of courses, recognition) ● Individual consultation

Collaboration and Stakeholder Engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Link between central administration and students ● Exam boards ● Partner institutions (departmental level)
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4. European University Alliance Manager	
General description	<p>The strong transformative potential of EUI involvement for the institutions becomes apparent in the key role apparent in strategy development, the strength and diversity of collaborative networks, and the empowerment of EUI coordinators and EUI activities on different levels.</p>
Strategic and Policy-Level Involvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Cooperates closely with HEI leadership ● represents the alliance in different councils and work packages, ● Involved in strategic development and setting of priorities ● Supervises activities eg in mobility clusters for strategic monitoring ● Transversal role in Working groups and Councils on cross-cutting themes, eg ED&I ● Mobility strategy: development of alliance-centered mobility opportunities, target group-specific analysis, and assessment of EUI impact
Mobility Management & Inclusion Practices	<p>Mobility Management</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Advising on mobility trends & formats for target groups ● Study success & Quality assurance
	<p>Inclusion Support</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Anchoring ED&I topics n EUI practices and activities ● Advising staff and students on Inclusion Support in the program ● Ensuring accessibility of offers, e.g. alliance-based courses

	Communication & Outreach <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Alliance-centered (online) promotion● Dissemination and advising on European/alliance level
Collaboration and Stakeholder Engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Leadership of HEI Rectors and Vice-Rectors for strategy development, lobbying, and in national contexts● Service Units<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Student Services on regulatory issues○ Accreditation offices et al: development of joint study offers & joint degrees○ Support Units & Student Counselling: standardization of EUI-related services; Welcome structures○ IT-Department: for joint digital infrastructure, shared learning platforms, access to/interconnectivity of HEI SIS and CMS○ Communication Dpt.: communication of EUI activities; creation of EUI corporate identity/label; enhancement of visibility and access of opportunities● Faculty<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Deans for cooperation, research cooperation, curricular development, and lobbying○ academic staff for cooperation in EUI activities, e.g. development of joint degrees, BIPs○ academics as participants in activities for increased impact and outreach of EUI● Students & student organisations<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ own EUI student union representing the EUI's student bodies○ EUI partners' student organisations or local ESN teams

5. Student Support & Counseling Staff	
General description	As centers of equity, diversity, inclusion and belonging, student support & counselling offices create an inclusive anti-discriminatory environment at the university through policy work and counselling. Responsible for systematic information management and individual counselling, usually focusing on degree-seeking students on all study levels, they hold the expertise on regulatory and legal frameworks.
Strategic and Policy-Level Involvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Responsible for general code of conduct and EDI strategy on central level ● Offer Guidelines for EDI compliance ● Support Awareness-raising & stakeholder-involvement
Mobility Management & Inclusion Practices	Mobility Management <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● translating the national system ● personal counselling in individual cases
	Inclusion Support <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Principle of equal treatment: same process for both national and international students ● services for various target groups (eg caregivers, students with disabilities, etc) ● counselling in cases of discrimination, verbal or physical transgression ● Legal advice
	Communication & Outreach <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ensuring visibility, lobbying for the target groups ● website and information material in the national language and potentially other languages ● participation in orientation & welcome events to introduce the services
Collaboration and Stakeholder Engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● HEI leadership ● deans of faculties ● IRO & Welcome Services

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Student representation • all members of the university who have been discriminated against
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6. Student Representative	
General description	<p>Student representatives have access to the student-related topics that pertain to student life and international experience on different levels and can thus introduce the student perspective in program design and implementation. In the context of their voluntary work, they offer peer-group support and advising.</p>
Strategic and Policy-Level Involvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutional student representations (student union, student parliament) can impact strategy development and institutional policy • representation in HEI political bodies • local ESN sections collaborate via ESN International for lobbying and policy-making
Mobility Management & Inclusion Practices	<p>Mobility Management</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • focus: Incoming students • Mentoring of international students • Social/cultural program • Support in everyday matters
	<p>Inclusion Support</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensuring accessibility of organized offers and events • Support with individual barriers, offering individual counselling; • socio-cultural integration
	<p>Communication & Outreach</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Outreach to (future) incoming students • Organisation of welcome days & cultural program

Collaboration and Stakeholder Engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● HEI administration● IROs, Erasmus-Offices● Collaboration with other student organisations, esp. the local ESN groups or ESN international● Outreach to Alumni of the mobility programmes
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Recommendations for Organisational Development

3. **Assign clear responsibilities to strengthen specialised support - and information services.**

To ensure quality-based programme management, institutions should ensure a clear assignment and definition of tasks and responsibilities to support staff engagement and successful administrative processes. Transparent internal structures increase the accessibility of information, and smooth internal communication.

4. **Foster transparent collaboration and open communication across institutional units.**

With clearly defined roles and responsibilities within the institutional units, units and individual staff involved in the mobility management can start a pro-active, open interaction with the different sectors of the HEI. Strengthening staff involvement and the sharing and transfer of information and knowledge based on the shared task or goal helps to establish resource-sensitive processes, reduces redundancies, and supports an integration of mobility-related tasks in the over-all structures supporting the student-life-cycle.

5. **Support of staff is an essential aspect of quality assurance and change management.**

Staff members are increasingly challenged by the amount and complexity of tasks and a changing work environment. Access to training/learning opportunities as well as a balanced, supportive work environment are essential for successful, impactful and sensitive change processes

